

Deliverable D3.6

Video demonstrator showing data access based on a pillar III use case

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable references and adds detail to Milestone 8 (Incremental Demonstrator) which demonstrates secure cross border access to genomic and phenotypic data for a GDI use case., adding use case specific workflows and utility to previous demonstrators, such as Milestone 7. The milestone demonstrated both a Cancer and Infectious disease use case, as well as an Allele Frequency browser which supports use cases from pharmacogenomics, rare disease, and public health screening.

The cancer disease use case has been demonstrated by discovering, applying and being granted access to synthetic cancer data, and subsequently performing an analysis on these data in a secure processing environment using cBioPortal. The infectious disease use case has been demonstrated by using the Allele Frequency browser to gain information on a genomic variant possibly associated with severe Covid-19, and as a stretch goal, by discovering, applying for, and being granted access to synthetic infectious disease data, and performing a remote GWAS analysis on these data to identify a range of variants which have an association with Covid-19 severity. These use cases show how this infrastructure can support the use of a use case specific data analysis platform, provide allele frequency data relevant to a range of use cases, and support investigation of both polygenic and monogenic disease.

The milestone was demonstrated by two presentations given at the GDI General Assembly in Lisbon in November 2024, and by two recorded videos, one for the Cancer use case and one about the Allele Frequency browser.

A total of six nodes participated in the milestone, each participating in their chosen use case.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 5</p>	No

<p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

Following on from Milestone 7, which had a set of nodes deployed with real-like synthetic data, nodes were invited to participate in Milestone 8 which aimed to demonstrate this infrastructure on at least one GDI use case. As each node has different capabilities and priorities, a planning meeting with the nodes was held to try and identify one or more possible use cases that the participating nodes would be able to support. Also relevant to the planning meeting were the availability of appropriate synthetic datasets. As a basis for the discussion, the deliverables D8.5¹ (Report on Federated Learning Technologies) and milestones 26² (Initial set of questions from the Use Cases) & 27³ (Initial set of relevant data for the Use Cases) from Pillar III were used, as well as a presentation⁴ from EUCAIM⁵ on Federated Computation from the ELIXIR AHM⁶ in June 2024⁷.

Figure 1: Generic User Journey, 1+MG functionalities, and associated products and services to be used to demonstrate the different Pillar III Use Cases from Milestone 7. This is the same user journey supported by milestone 8, with the exception that the Allele Frequency Browser user story is supported by only the first 3 stages of the user journey described above.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11550561>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289476>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.115972>

⁴ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1PBMeVux-ukXoCsj8mAaUf_c3oHWCYwam5cpc37WTKY4/edit#slide=id.g2e3832b6d94_1_37

⁵ <https://cancerimage.eu/>

⁶ <https://elixir-events.eventscase.com/EN/ahm2024>

⁷ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1ROIUOTayf8JcDYNa-Je1KMGH5sK2Pq6TJoNb2eC2II/edit>

The result of the meeting was that two GDI Use Cases (referring to the GDI use cases from WP7 - T7.3 and T7.4) were initially leveraged to perform the demonstration of the GDI infrastructure. User scenarios and user stories were defined from the requirements of the two use cases, where a user story is a high level requirement that a user has, while a scenarios extends a story to give specifics and details. Three scenarios were created from the two use cases, and one user story that can support these scenarios - the Infectious Disease (scenarios 1 & 2) and Cancer (scenarios 3). The infectious disease use case gave two specific user scenarios⁸, one each for monogenic (scenario 1, see below) and polygenic (scenario 2, see below) susceptibility. However, after associated discussions with Pillar I regarding demonstrating clinical utility, and leveraging a set of Genome of Ireland user stories originally presented in the cross pillar meeting in Malta⁹ in March 2024, it became apparent that the monogenic infectious disease user scenario could be supported by the allele frequency user story (4 below) and hence address a greater range of different user scenarios and use cases related to, for example, cancer and pharmacogenomics. Therefore this user story was separated and called the allele frequency user story, with the Infectious Disease monogenic scenario (1) a specific instance of this user story. All the user scenarios and stories can be supported by the same infrastructure and user journey shown in Figure 1, with the Allele Frequency user story supported by the first three stages of the user journey.

1 - The monogenic Infectious Disease scenario is as follows:

A team wants to try and understand why a particular young man with COVID-19 has severe symptoms but there are no demographic factors that can explain a risk of severe symptoms. There are sequencing data available from this individual, and a variant is found in the TLR7 gene, which has previously been linked to severe COVID-19, but this particular variant has not been observed by the team before. The team enters the variant into the Allele Frequency Browser of the GDI to quickly see if this variant has been seen in other individuals across Europe, and if so, the allele frequency of this variant within that country.

2 - The polygenic Infectious Disease scenario is as follows:

A team wants to quickly identify common risk variants for severe COVID-19 to help understand the disease etiology. To do this, the team wants to perform the same GWAS analysis¹⁰ across data hosted in different countries without moving the data. The team finds applicable data in the GDI, and submit an access request using their LS Login¹¹ identity, which provides the user with a unique electronic identity with which to access the infrastructure. After the access request is approved, the team submits their GWAS analysis from their local computer to the Finnish Secure Processing Environment (SPE), where the GWAS analysis is performed. The results of the analysis, when complete, are accessible after login in using their LS Login identity.

⁸ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1EY6NyoR2YwiXQc1JkYSTHs8QInL4OTB6/edit#slide=id.pg>

⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1iiLA5J7VGOen3RgSJ2NuxPxYrvWocbP6ZV8ZE-ciU7Q/edit?pli=1&tab=t.o>

¹⁰ https://github.com/Ax-Sch/asso_smk_smpl

¹¹ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login.html>

3 - The Cancer scenario is as follows:

A researcher is investigating colorectal cancer, and uses GDI to search for relevant datasets which have female participants with colorectal cancer. They discover an applicable dataset in the Norwegian node via a Beacon query, and apply for access. After access is granted, the researcher uses cBioPortal to investigate the data, especially the cell cycle progression for particular genetic variants.

4 - Allele Frequency User Story

A user (either clinical or research) wants to quickly know the prevalence of a particular genetic variant in a specific cohort, to help prioritise for further investigation a set of candidate genetic variants. They navigate to the GDI Allele Frequency (AF) browser¹², and enter the genetic variant. They receive a response detailing the frequency of that variant in the different datasets within GDI.

Having chosen one or more user stories / scenarios, each node needed to deploy the required products or provide the required services (summarised in Table 1 and detailed in section 4) to support the necessary functionalities for their chosen demonstration. Each node entered their progress on a Zenhub¹³ board, so progress could be monitored and tracked between nodes.

	Luxembourg	Norway	Finland	Portugal	Spain	Sweden
AF Browser			✓	✓	✓	✓
AF Beacon			✓	✓	✓	✓
User Portal Data Catalogue	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
User Portal REMS	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
FDP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Beacon	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Beacon Network	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
LS Login	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sensitive Data Archive	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

¹² <https://af-browser-demo.ega-archive.org/>

¹³ <https://app.zenhub.com/workspaces/milestone-8-deployment-6690ebaccf32eb000f5df5b0/board>

Synthetic Data	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
htsget				✓		✓
SPE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
cBioPortal	✓	✓				
TES API			✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Outline of the products and services each node deployed or connected to, to support the necessary functionalities for their chosen demonstration, with the Allele Frequency browser in green, common products and services in red, the cancer demonstration in blue, and the infectious disease demonstration in orange.

4. Description of work accomplished

All nodes that deployed services for the milestone utilised synthetic data for demonstration purposes, as the GDI currently does not have the legal framework to support the use of real genomic and phenotypic data.

The cancer use case was demonstrated using the colorectal cancer dataset¹⁴, while the allele frequency and infectious disease use cases were demonstrated using a subset of a 1+MG synthetic dataset of 1 million individuals generated by THL¹⁵ in support of the 1+MG declaration, which is currently only available for use within GDI and 1+MG. This dataset contained individuals with severe Covid-19 caused by the monogenic mutation in the TLR7 gene, as well as less severe covid symptoms which were polygenic in origin and suitable for the genome wide association analysis (GWAS). This dataset comprises individuals originally identified as from Italy, Finland, and German - however in the milestone only Finland from the three countries deployed a node so the populations were randomly assigned to the different nodes.

4.1 Finland

The Finnish GDI node is utilising the existing Sensitive Data Services¹⁶ (SDS) infrastructure, which is also used for the Finnish Federated EGA¹⁷ node, to support the required functionalities necessary for an operational GDI node. These include provision for the Storage and Interfaces, Data Access and Management, Data Reception, and Data Analysis. The Storage and Interfaces and Data Reception functionality are utilised in GDI as deployed in SDS, although there are specific differences in the functionalities for the SDS and GDI specific requirements for the Data Access management, Data Analysis, and Data Discovery functionalities.

¹⁴ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000564>

¹⁵ <https://thl.fi/etusivu>

¹⁶ <https://research.csc.fi/sensitive-data>

¹⁷ <https://docs.csc.fi/data/sensitive-data/federatedega/>

For Data Access and Management, the Finnish node can read and act upon the permissions held within a GA4GH ControlledAccessGrants¹⁸ Visa issued by the User Portal's¹⁹ REMS, facilitating the access management of GDI permissions centrally via the User Portal's REMS. However, to access CSC compute resources, including SD Desktop²⁰ and ePouta²¹, the user must have already registered a user account at CSC and linked it with their LS Login²² Identity.

For Data Analysis, a stretch goal within the Milestone for the Infectious Disease polygenic user scenario, a development task execution service²³ (TES) endpoint was utilised to allow a task to be submitted, and the results accessed, from a remote location, with the data analysis performed in the ePouta IaaS Cloud service for sensitive data. Utilising the TES endpoint, a task was submitted to run a GWAS pipeline as supplied by 1+MG WG11 (Infectious Disease), and this was executed on publicly available 1000 Genomes data²⁴.

For Data Discovery, GDI requires the deployment of a Beacon²⁵ and a Fair Data Point²⁶ (FDP) to allow the User Portal to support the relevant discovery functionality. The FDP is used to populate the data catalogue in the User Portal, while the Beacon allows users, who have logged into the portal, to discover the different phenotypes at an individual level within a dataset.

An additional Allele Frequency (AF) specific Beacon was deployed for the allele frequency use case, whereby a user could utilise the updated Beacon network to perform a federated analysis of anonymous aggregate data to discover country or cohort specific allele frequencies. One of the requirements for the AF specific beacon is that all data in the beacon are not personal data, and in this case the data are aggregated data of allele frequencies only.

For the milestone, the node deployed a GDI specific FDP, separate Beacon and AF Beacon with individual level and aggregate data respectively, and internet accessible proxy with LS Login authentication which passed the submitted TES compatible task to a TESK²⁷ deployed on the ePouta IaaS cloud. The TESK instance can install anything in a repository or container as specified in the task description, but this can be restricted on the proxy that is used to enable this access. TESK is also workflow manager agnostic, so could interface with Galaxy²⁸ or Nextflow²⁹ for example, and follows

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030>

¹⁹ <https://portal.dev.gdi.lu/>

²⁰ <https://sd-desktop.csc.fi/quacamole/#/>

²¹ <https://research.csc.fi/-/epouta>

²² <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

²³ <https://ga4gh.github.io/task-execution-schemas/docs/>

²⁴ <https://www.internationalgenome.org/>

²⁵ <https://docs.genomebeacons.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.fairdatapoint.org/>

²⁷ <https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/TESK>

²⁸ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.nextflow.io/>

the loosely coupled approach described in D8.5³⁰ to reduce vendor lock-in and help ensure different use cases can use their tools of choice.

4.2 Luxembourg

The Luxembourgish GDI node is provisioned on ELIXIR-LU's³¹ OpenStack³² infrastructure. The deployment comprises several components - Storages and Interfaces (S&I), Beacon v2 Production Implementation (B2PI)³³, Molgenis³⁴ (acting as DCAT³⁵ compatible meta-data exchange Fair Data Point, FDP) and cBioPortal³⁶ running within a Secure Processing Environment (SPE).

In order to demonstrate the Cancer use-case, a subset of synthetic colorectal cancer dataset³⁷ developed for use with EOSC4Cancer³⁸ has been loaded into S&I, Beacon and cBioPortal. The respective meta-data has been loaded into FDP and automatically harvested into GDI Data Catalogue hosted at the User Portal³⁹. Luxembourgish node uses GA4GH Visas embedded in LS:AAI user profiles issued by the User Portal's REMS to handle authorization to the datasets.

Beacon has been successfully registered into Beacon Network. Access to the SPE is facilitated using Apache Guacamole⁴⁰ and protected with F5 Web Application Firewall⁴¹ (WAF).

4.3 Norway

The Norwegian GDI node is deployed in the same national infrastructure for sensitive data (TSD - Tjenester for Sensitive Data⁴²) as the Federated EGA Norway node⁴³. The architecture is composed of layered security zones, with an internet connected proxy server in one security zone and back-end servers inside a TSD project area isolated from the internet. The services can only communicate between these two zones using restricted and audited communication through an AMQP⁴⁴ message passing interface and a Representational State Transfer (REST) based file operation API, both secured with strong authentication and encrypted communication.

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11550560>

³¹ <https://elixir-luxembourg.org/>

³² <https://www.openstack.org/>

³³ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/beacon2-pi-api>

³⁴ <https://github.com/molgenis/molgenis-emx2>

³⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

³⁶ <https://www.cbioportal.org/>

³⁷ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000564>

³⁸ <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

³⁹ <https://portal.dev.gdi.lu/>

⁴⁰ <https://guacamole.apache.org/>

⁴¹ <https://www.f5.com/glossary/web-application-firewall-waf>

⁴² <https://www.uio.no/tsd>

⁴³ <https://ega.elixir.no/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.amqp.org/>

The node contains a deployment of Storage and Interfaces (S&I) containing the complete EOSC4Cancer⁴⁵ Colorectal Cancer Synthetic dataset⁴⁶ generated in Norway, a Beacon v2 Reference Implementation instance serving the indexed meta-data of the synthetic cancer data set, and a DCAT⁴⁷ compatible meta-data exchange⁴⁸ FDP for the GDI User Portal to harvest and populate the Dataset meta-data into GDI Data Catalogue hosted at the User Portal.

For Data Access and Management, the Norwegian node can read and act upon the permissions held within a GA4GH ControlledAccessGrants⁴⁹ Visa issued by the User Portal⁵⁰, facilitating the access management of GDI permissions centrally via the User Portal.

For Data Analysis, access was requested to the Colorectal Cancer Synthetic Dataset, approved, and transferred to an isolated new project area inside TSD available to the data requester to access. The transfer was done with the GDI services respecting the visa granting access and signed by User Portal REMS⁵¹. In the Norwegian trusted research environment (TRE), the GDI support team had assisted in the setup of a cBioPortal container importing the Colorectal Cancer Synthetic Dataset to be ready for further in-depth study and exploration by the cancer expert that requested the data.

4.4 Portugal

The Portuguese GDI node is deployed in the same OpenStack infrastructure as the Portuguese Federated EGA (FEGA). The node contains a deployment of Beacon v2 Production Implementation⁵², Beacon v2 for Allele frequencies⁵³, REMS⁵⁴, htsgset⁵⁵, Storage and Interfaces (S&I)⁵⁶, TES (using a dockerized Funnel)⁵⁷ and a Fair Data Point (FDP)⁵⁸.

Regarding Data Access and Management, the Portuguese node uses GA4GH Visas to control access to S&I files with dataset granularity, the accepted Visa Issuers for the Portuguese node are the User

⁴⁵ <https://eosc4cancer.eu/>

⁴⁶ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000564>

⁴⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

⁴⁸ <https://github.com/Health-RI/SeMPyRO>

⁴⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030>

⁵⁰ <https://portal.dev.gdi.lu/>

⁵¹ <https://daam.portal.dev.gdi.lu/>

⁵² <https://beacon-prod.gdi.biodata.pt/api>

⁵³ <https://beacon-alleles.gdi.biodata.pt/api>

⁵⁴ <https://rems.gdi.biodata.pt>

⁵⁵ <https://htsgset.gdi.biodata.pt>

⁵⁶ <https://login.gdi.biodata.pt>

⁵⁷ <https://tes.gdi.biodata.pt>

⁵⁸ <https://fdp.gdi.biodata.pt>

Portal's REMS⁵⁹, and the Portuguese REMS. This setup allows users coming either from an European or a national context to easily access data stored.

For Data Analysis, there was a goal within the Milestone 8 for the Infectious Disease scenario that would allow users to run a predefined pipeline on a frontend that used S&I and Funnel⁶⁰ (TES API) on the backside. It was not possible to run the pipeline successfully at the Portuguese node due to an incompatibility between the files of the use case and the pipeline.

For Data Discovery, there is a Beacon v2 instance and an FDP to allow the User Portal (UP) to support the relevant discovery functionality. The FDP is populated locally with all the metadata referring to datasets and files that belong to them, while the Beacon v2 helps users find relevant datasets by querying phenotypes in the UP, which uses Beacon Network (BN) as a middle-agent to take care of querying and aggregating responses from each node. The dataset of the use case was quite lengthy, so a repository⁶¹ from Health-RI was used. The repository contained code to automatically validate and upload metadata to an FDP, as well as a specific example of metadata for GDI. This example was replicated and modified in a GitHub fork⁶² so a batch of files were uploaded to the FDP by receiving a tab separated file with the filename and accession ID of each file as an input.

There was also a use case for an Allele Frequency (AF) Beacon, requiring a separate Beacon instance containing aggregated data about allele counts and nothing about phenotypic or individual data. The allele count data included, for each variant: the allele frequency, the total allele count, the count of homozygous alleles, and the count of heterozygous alleles. Apart from that, it worked similarly to the regular Beacon, being connected to a BN⁶³ compatible with the AF schema to aggregate responses from different nodes and display them to users.

4.5 Spain

The Spanish GDI node infrastructure is divided between the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). CRG manages the Fair Datapoint Point (FDP), Beacon, Allele Frequency deployment, and European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA) instances, while BSC deployed the open Virtual Research Environment (openVRE), a cloud platform for the execution of tools.

The Spanish node recognises LS Login as an identity provider. In order to access data, the Spanish node requires users to link their EGA account to their LS Login identity. Afterwards, the GA4GH Visas issued by the User Portal's REMS and associated with their LS Login identity are processed. These visas grant access to users to a list of datasets, which should be approved in their EGA account.

⁵⁹ <https://daam.portal.dev.gdi.lu>

⁶⁰ <https://github.com/ohsu-comp-bio/funnel>

⁶¹ <https://github.com/Health-RI/SeMPyRO>

⁶² <https://github.com/FracassandoCasualmente/SeMPyRO>

⁶³ <https://af-browser-demo.ega-archive.org>

For data analysis, a new Task Execution Service (TES) endpoint was developed as part of the openVRE to allow the execution of a task via API. Given that TES allows the execution of arbitrary code, requests in this regard are severely limited, meaning that only some particular workflows can be executed. For Milestone 8, the required GWAS pipeline on infectious disease data was launched but the execution failed at some point because of some unresolved internal error of the pipeline.

4.6 Sweden

The Swedish GDI node is deployed in the same infrastructure, (CIS⁶⁴ compliant Kubernetes installation), as the Swedish Federated EGA. The node contains a deployment of Beacon v2 Production Implementation containing the aggregate allele frequency data, for the allele frequency browser, - htsget, Storage and Interfaces (S&I), TES and a Fair Data Point.

Regarding Data Access and Management, the Swedish node uses GA4GH Visas to control access to S&I files with dataset granularity, the accepted Visa Issuers for the Swedish node are the User Portal's REMS.

The deployed TES implementation is a flavor of Funnel that supports fetching data that a user has been granted access to through a visa, directly from the S&I Sensitive Data Archive⁶⁵ (SDA) and making them available as input to the user's submitted compute task in a secure way. For output of computation results, a pre-configured private S3 bucket is used to which access can be given on-demand to users for downloading their computation results.

For the Data Analysis, a task can be submitted to Funnel's API to run the GWAS pipeline on data pulled from the SDA. Due to limitations to the allocated compute infrastructure at the time of the milestone (VMs of 16G each), only a population subset from one chromosome was used.

Ultimately, through submitting a task to Funnel's API the GWAS pipeline was successfully run on the Swedish infrastructure with data from the assigned dataset.

5. Results

- Six nodes deployed an infrastructure for participation within Milestone 8

⁶⁴ <https://www.cisecurity.org/>

⁶⁵ <https://neic-sda.readthedocs.io/en/latest/services/sda/>

- 3 user scenarios and 1 user story from 2 use cases have been demonstrated, with each node participating in at least 1 user scenario or story
- Presentations⁶⁶ and videos were utilised to demonstrate the deployed infrastructure, with videos as part of the Milestone

Six nodes (Finland, Luxembourg, Norway, Portugal, Spain, and Sweden) deployed a node using synthetic data as part of the milestone. The technical capabilities of the nodes are different (as described above), as each node has different priorities and requirements for the GDI infrastructure. This diversity of node setup demonstrates the power of the core infrastructure, supporting the same user interactions using different deployments and products where necessary, with the interoperability specified via existing standards and APIs where necessary.

All nodes utilised the Beacon, LS AAI, Beacon Network, Allele Frequency Browser, and the User Portal, however the nodes deployed different types of Fair Data Points, such as Molgenis or the FAIR Data point Reference Implementation. Additionally Spain utilised their existing EGA infrastructure to manage the data access permissions internally, mapping the LS AAI identity to the internal EGA identity.

Specifically for the milestone, two use cases were demonstrated, the cancer use case and a cross-cutting allele frequency use case.

To demonstrate the cancer use case, the whole process was recorded in a video⁶⁷. The deployments used included the centrally deployed User Portal and the Norway node with the discovery and data access request were performed centrally, and then access was facilitated at the Norwegian node. The data accessed in the video was the Colorectal Cancer Synthetic dataset, and this was made available in the Norwegian SPE (TSD⁶⁸) via a VM hosting an instance of cBioPortal.

The allele frequency use case was demonstrated by a presentation and live demonstration at the GDI General Assembly, and also by a video recording⁶⁹.

6. Discussion

- Six nodes deployed
 - 1 demonstrated the Cancer Use case
 - 1 demonstrated the Infectious Disease Use Case 1
 - 4 nodes demonstrated the Allele Frequency Use Case via the Infectious Disease use Case 2
- Not achieved
 - Federated access management
 - Unified and harmonised metadata

⁶⁶ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1eRt6oFPTYIFnTDUGgZKUUbflqYG4QLJp8OmCUvfehPQ/edit#slide=id.g3140ee742c1_0_11

⁶⁷ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/13DLNX9-Huxo8b0P9waLy2C9Xg-OQ1k7O/view?usp=sharing>

⁶⁸ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/about/description-of-the-system.html>

⁶⁹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mZA6JUaKVi5vK3Rrz-1lc2UlmqkGgLoP/view>

- Integration of the Allele Frequency browser into the User Portal
 - Including support for anonymous level queries
- Acceptance of 'Terms & Conditions' and outline of research question before performing Beacon queries over individual level data
- Improved UX for AAI and SPE / TES endpoint access

In Milestone 8 the access and permissions management providing controlled access to datasets is performed by the REMS system, as part of the User Portal. However, it is still an open question on whether this will be the final methodology of permissions management, or whether a federated solution is required where each node controls their own permissions once those permissions have been granted, a federated access and permissions management system. The latter is preferable as it conforms to a 'zero-trust' approach as required by the NIS2⁷⁰ regulations. However, it will also require the development of a specific 'Data Access and Access management' API that would support the management of permissions in such a federated context. Additionally this means that there still is not full support for the 1+MG Data Governance, which details the 1+MG Data Access Committee (DAC) recommendation and National Coordination Point (NCP) veto process, however the veto can be actioned within the centralised system and enforced with developments to the workflow within REMS. These issues have been noted and are actively being addressed between the User Portal, REMS, and AAI product teams.

As described, each node was free to support a particular use case from WP7 based on their own national priorities. However, the collective deployments show that the core infrastructure will support all three use cases, including the data model. The only difference in deployments for the different use cases is the type of platform (e.g. cBioPortal for the cancer use case) used for the data analysis, which is use case dependent. Importantly the Beacon and FDP data models are flexible enough to support the different use cases, as is the access model. Federated analysis is an expected requirement for the different use cases, and has been partially demonstrated using the Infectious disease use case via GWAS analysis, however the TES standard is use case agnostic and can accept tasks for genomic and phenotypic data analysis irrespective of the use case, and can also interface with different orchestrators or workflow managers, such as Nextflow or Galaxy.

Another foreseen issue was the lack of a harmonised metadata model for the User Portal ensuring that the same ontologies, terms and core information was shared across the different nodes. This resulted in different nodes responding to different queries, depending on how the query was formed or which ontology was used. This issue is being addressed via 1+MG WG3 and GDI WP8.2, who are defining the minimal metadata model. This issue extends to the representation of the data within a Beacon instance, as each Beacon allows additional individual level metadata to be queried by users who have logged into the User Portal. Once the minimal metadata model has been defined, this can be mapped to both the FDP and the Beacon model (where required), ensuring harmonised queries across the different nodes. Note that for the genomic variants, currently all nodes utilise the same

⁷⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022L2555>

annotation pipeline so variant annotation is the same across nodes, and work is ongoing on how to ensure the metadata responses of a Beacon and FDP are in sync and equivalent.

A major achievement of the Milestone was the development and deployment of the Allele Frequency browser, which leverages the Beacon standard to enable AF queries over aggregated, and hence non-personal data, which supports data discovery for all GDI use cases and beyond. As part of the user engagement into GDI it would be beneficial to integrate the allele frequency query with the main user portal, forming a clear progression for users through the different access levels and hence encouraging interaction with the data. This would also help demystify the data within GDI, which could also help increase participant or citizen engagement. However the User Portal would need a redesign to support this process, and this work is ongoing.

Part of the Data Governance is that to perform a Beacon query that processes personal data (such as the query for females who have colorectal cancer in the Cancer demonstration), even if the response is not personal or identifiable, the user needs to indicate acceptance of a set of Terms and Conditions, as well as describe the research purpose they wish to make these queries for, to conform to GDPR. This need has been identified, and scheduled for development.

The video and the presentation at the GDI GA in November both demonstrate the 'copy and paste' of access tokens to access compute and/or data resources that the user has the permission to access. This is suboptimal from the user experience perspective, but also does not conform to the zero-trust requirements needed to conform to NIS2. The need for improvement has been identified, and proposals are being worked on to enable a solution to be found.

Only one node was able to try and demonstrate distributed, as opposed to federated, computation, which was an original stretch goal of the milestone. However a demonstration deployment of a way to receive tasks or workflows into an SPE was demonstrated. The deployed version of a TES endpoint in this case, TESK, differs from the product in the starter kit and demonstrates the importance of using standard APIs to maximise interoperability and minimise vendor lock-in as products can be replaced or changed as required. Consideration must be given to restricting the source of the containers or repositories that the TESK instance can access, and this would help limit the possible analyses that can be performed on the data. The demonstration used the command line to submit the task, however this would be expected to be run from an orchestrator when the infrastructure is in production and this could be accessible via the User Portal. The results of the data were uploaded to an s3 bucket accessible only to the authorised user via LS Login, however this could be changed to a file server accessible via the User Portal for example, improving the user experience and enable the submission of the task and accessing of the results from the same interface.

Most of the issues described above had been foreseen, either prior to or during deployment, and have been, or will be scheduled for development. The scope of the final infrastructure is being finalised in Q1 of 2025, and once that is done solutions to all issues can be documented.

7. Conclusions & Impact

Milestone 8 has demonstrated the utility of the core GDI infrastructure to a range of use cases, including two specific use cases within GDI WP7 but also others outside of GDI, particularly with the Allele Frequency browser which demonstrates supports pharmacogenomics, rare & infectious disease, as well as public health screening⁷¹ while not using personal data. Data discovery has been demonstrated using different queries from different use cases, as well as different types of data analyses based on the requirements of the use cases.

Due to the lack of the necessary legal framework, such as an EDIC⁷² for the GDI, real genomic and phenotypic data cannot be utilised within the GDI, hence the necessity to use synthetic data for demonstration purposes. These data accurately mimic the data types, format, and content of the real data expected to be accessed and analysed within the GDI.

8. Next steps

Now the final demonstration milestone has been performed, the focus of GDI is to the productionisation and deployment of the infrastructure. The deployed infrastructure described here will form the basis of the feature freeze due in February 2025, where the features and functionalities the operational node needs to provide will be confirmed, as described in section 6.

Part of the productionisation of the infrastructure is to perform the necessary risk analyses and data protection impact assessments across the whole infrastructure, including the operational processes and procedures as well as the core technical infrastructure. This work will proceed– in conjunction with WP4.

⁷¹ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1r75XC1DxkYxLD_sHaSSnDQW1qng-ptp7heRSI_ZwPkoo/edit#slide=id.g3150bc605d9_2_92

⁷² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/edic>

